
EXPERIMENTAL MACHINE LEARNING OF FINGER PHOTOPLETHYSMOGRAPHY (PPG) FOR AUTONOMOUS HOSPITAL BED PUSHING FRAMEWORK USING POLYNOMIAL REGRESSION

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Abstract:

In community-based healthcare, the nursing workforce requires low-skilled nursing automation in the hospital to accelerate talent development towards high-skilled advance practice nurse for community deployment. As precursor, the hospital bed pushing operation for medium-risk patient was hypothesized as a novice nursing task where artificial intelligence automation is possible. The solution framework was embodied by a concept of operation with non-invasive vitals monitoring as priority to study feasibility in addressing patient life-safety requirements. Polynomial regression machine learning of 65 one-hour sets of finger PPG data from a single subject were collected and studied. Convergence of finger PPG to 8th degree polynomial was observed which suggested process feasibility towards establishing patient safe states during autonomous journey. Process reliability ranged between 2% to 95% with long PPG counts as influencing factor for drops in reliability score.

Motivation/Background: *A predictable non-invasive vitals monitoring was priority to enable autonomous hospital bed pushing framework to address patient life-safety concerns during autonomous journey. Finger PPG is a non-invasive and easy to use method to monitor heart related activities and used to study for convergence and reliability within the framework.*

Method: *65 one-hour sets of finger PPG was recorded from a single male, age 27 subject. The data was processed by polynomial regression machine learning technique to output the degree of polynomial with highest cross validation score mean.*

Results: *Convergence of regressed PPG data to 8th degree for both pre-journey and journey datasets and degree of polynomial matching reliability of 2% to 95% were observed.*

Conclusions: *Convergence of PPG data facilitates the establishment of safe physical states in vitals monitoring, enabling the autonomous hospital bed pushing framework for further development. Reliability remains an area for improvement via medical grade.*

Keywords: Machine Learning; Polynomial Regression; Photoplethysmography; Autonomous Hospital Bed Pushing; Vitals Monitoring; Nursing.

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1. Introduction

Nursing in Singapore is transforming to meet the healthcare demands based on projected increase of Singapore residents of age 65 and above through 2030[1]. This transformation was driven by aging-in-place healthcare strategy where seniors are enabled to stay healthy through activities and affordable healthcare options within the immediate community. 3 paradigm shifts are predicted to realize this transformation, namely: (1) health promotion, (2) care in the community and (3) affordable care[1]. Resulting from the extension of healthcare services into the community, nurses of aging-in-place healthcare can expect to be autonomous in making medical decisions as they take on more challenging clinical tasks within the community. The nature of autonomy is similar to an Advance Practice Nurse (APN) in the existing healthcare framework. Since APN is a highly-skilled position, nursing transformation in Singapore has been planned to develop more APNs by providing more career progression path ways. As accelerated skill progression of existing and incoming nurses towards APNs and community deployment takes place for aging-in-place healthcare, this would inherently require automation of low-skilled nursing tasks particularly within the hospital.

The Dreyfus Skill Acquisition Model [2, 3] was leveraged in this work for (1) its adaptation in nursing which aids in classification of low to high skilled nursing task and (2) the automation limits that model's philosophy imposes on Artificial Intelligence (AI)[2], such that automation of the mental activities of a nurse in the operation can be appropriate to the fullest extent. The model was incepted in during a study to describe behaviors of US air force pilot trainees in learning to fly[4] and adapted to the nursing setting to facilitate a descriptive study of expert nurses to identify areas of expert nursing competencies[5]. These are life-safety professions which deserve a mention to emphasize the model's rigor as the "without conscious" [2] a rational mode of thinking dominates the Proficiency, Expert and Mastery stages of Dreyfus Skill Acquisition Model can be easily misrepresented as irrational arguments by skeptics who do not agree with a trichotomy of thinking. The model's first adaptation to nursing offers behavioral description of a novice in nursing tasks determine fluid balance to be rule based and objective attributes focused as task outcomes [5], which in principle of the model suggests a suitable AI automation exist for similar tasks. Hence as precursor of this work, the hospital bed pushing operation, which involves vitals monitoring as discussed later, was hypo the sized as a novice nursing task with full automation of the nurse theoretically possible.

The conventional hospital bed pushing operation requires minimum of 2 persons (1 nurse, 1 porter) or more to move a hospital bed within the facility depending on the state of wellbeing of the transported patient. The operation has been viewed by researchers as menial, manpower inefficient and harmful to operator's health which guided research to eliminate these negative effects by reducing the minimum number of operators. An evaluation of commercial hospital bed mover solutions concluded the use of such solutions would lower muscle activation during 1-person operation[6] while anomni-directional bed mover prototype was concluded to have even lower muscle activation than existing solutions while improving maneuverability[7]. Perhaps the closest work to full automation is a semi-autonomous motorized hospital bed mover to transport patients with head injury [8] which demonstrated hands free mobility of the hospital bed that was intended to prevent further head injuries potentially caused by manual handling of the hospital bed. The body of research surrounding the hospital bed pushing operation inherently used a 1-person

operation framework as a desired objective where the operator is in the immediate vicinity of the hospital bed. Since there is no known fully autonomous hospital bed moving framework, it is a research gap to identify enabling automation technologies.

The experimental framework for fully autonomous hospital bed moving was embodied through a preliminary concept of operation for a medium risk patient and categorized by 3 phases: (1) Pre-journey; (2) Journey and (3) Emergency. As comparison, a medium-risk patient might be a hospitalized person who is bedridden and unlikely to require immediate medical attention which contrasts with low-risk patients who are wheelchair-bound or free to move about and high-risk patients who require immediate medical response like in intensive care units. The scope of users includes (1) Medium-risk patient; (2) Nurse; (3) Receiver; (4) Emergency Response, assumed to be 1 person; (5) Bystanders. During the first phase, pre-journey, the Nurse would conduct a wellbeing assessment of the Medium risk patient for autonomous journey which includes stable vital signs. As first guidance, the pre-journey phase should be completed in 5 minutes using non-invasive measurement devices for the ease of use for Nurse and Medium risk patient. Only when the Nurse is satisfied with the assessment the operation can proceed to the next phases. During autonomous journey, the hospital bed would depart from the starting location towards an Autonomous Ground Vehicle (AGV) zone located in the vicinity and practically, exposure to Bystanders during this short section is inevitable. The bulk of the journey is in an AGV zone isolated from Bystanders to minimize accidents and infection risks as the hospital bed moves to its destination within the hospital. The hospital bed would exit the AGV at the short distance from its destination. Like the start of journey, this is a short section and exposure to Bystanders is inevitable. At the destination, a Receiver is located at the destination to usher in the Medium risk patient for next action. The entire journey phase should not take more than 45 minutes considering the size of a multi-story, multi-building hospital. The emergency phase is auxiliary to address potential complications during autonomous journey. During emergency, which is triggered by abnormalities in the Medium-risk patient's vitals, the hospital bed should come to a stop at the nearest pre-designated location and await Emergency response's arrival. If immediate resuscitation is required, the hospital bed should provide a non-rolling and stable platform allow Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR) on a medically designed hard mattress. Since hallway care increases the chance of poor outcomes in emergency context[9], the better procedure is to manually transport the hospital bed by a single person to an alternative destination for further action. Resulting, the focus of this work is studying the feasibility of AI automated and non-invasive vitals monitoring to address the life-safety concerns during autonomous journey using photoplethysmography (PPG) at the finger as the preferred method to monitor heart activities.

The AI automation of novice nursing task comes as the use of machine learning's polynomial regression driven by the autonomous hospital bed pushing framework to compare the degree of polynomial of regressed PPG functions. Such an approach is plausible as existing electrocardiography (ECG) modelling suggests there is order in heart phenomena despite of heart variations as indicated by a segmented polynomial regression modelling of ECG which demonstrated a 94% and more accuracy in ST-T analysis[10]. With an ordered phenomenon, the life-safety of the Medium-risk patient addressed by immediately determining whether the status-quo has been violated, leading to accidents. Hence this work's objectives are (1) study the convergence of PPG's degree of polynomial within the autonomous hospital bed pushing

framework; (2) determine the reliability of matching the degree of polynomial between pre-journey and journey phases.

There is convergence of PPG to the 8th degree polynomial with room for hardware improvement for reliability range of 2.0% to 95.0%. Rest of the paper is as follows, section 2 will cover the data methods and collection of this work, section 3 will present an overall analysis across all 65 experimental runs followed by selected runs which are representative for discussion, section 4 concludes the study with its significance to the autonomous hospital bed pushing framework and improvements for future developments.

2. Materials and Methods

The autonomous hospital bed pushing framework provided the scope of method of data collection and processing to obtain degree of polynomial matching of regressed PPG data.

In this study, a run of PPG data serves as representation of a successful autonomous hospital bed pushing operation. A count was segmented by a heartbeat which rises to 50% signal amplitude of the steepest PPG ascend. Sets served as collections of counts within a run.

For a run, a pre-journey set consisted of the first 240 counts of heartbeat, which approximates to 4 minutes and represents Nurse verified PPG during the pre-journey phase. These are counts 2 to 242 within a run to filter hardware startup noise. The remaining PPG data in the run was segmented in non-overlapping journey sets of 30 heartbeat counts under guidance of central limit theorem's significant sample size to represent PPG from Medium-risk patient's journey.

Since the best fitting polynomial will always unknown at the start of a run, it was calculated directly from the sets within a run in this study. For every polynomial degree from 0 to 19, using python's scikit-learn polynomial machine learning, a program distributed data within a set at a ratio of 80:20 training-test data ratio with 30 cross validation fold and the regressed model was evaluated using cross validation score mean. The best degree of polynomial was determined by the best cross validation score mean across 0 to 19 degree. The process was repeated for each set within a run and will generate a best fitting degree of polynomial for each set within a run. The degree of polynomial of best fit from the journey sets is matched to the pre-journey set, a match would have both degree of polynomial to be the same.

The framework driven method and nature of this study resulted in the following materials:

Table 1: Materials used in study

Hardware		
Item Description	Quantity	Purpose
Pulse Sensor	1	PPG sensor by World Famous Electronics LLC.
Arduino Mega	1	Microcontroller to capture PPG sensor data.
USB A to USB B cable	1	Data connection between Arduino and Laptop.
Laptop, ASUS UX430U	1	Data processing platform.
Bed	1	Facilitate lying down posture.
Chair	1	Facilitate sitting up posture.

Software		
Item Description	Version	Purpose
Arduino IDE	1.8.5	Flashing program to Arduino Mega.
Pulse Sensor Library	1.1	Sense PPG at 50 Hz sampling rate.
CoolTerm	1.5.0	Record data stream from Arduino to Laptop.
Visual Studio 2017 Community	15.7.6	Facilitate Python development environment.
Anaconda Python Environment	5.1.0	Python distribution.

65 one-hour runs were conducted at random hours between 04 August 2018 to 23 August 2018 on a single subject male, age 27. For each run, the pulse sensor was fixed onto the left middle finger tip of the subject. Posture of a run was randomized and limited to lying down in bed or sitting in chair to represent potential postures during an autonomous hospital bed pushing journey. The subject remains in that posture until the one-hour has past.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Convergence of PPG Data from Pre-Journey Sets

For pre-journey set of each run, polynomial regression of PPG data converged at the 8th degree polynomial, shown in Figure 1. CVSM peaked at 8th degree polynomial with 0.91 and was the lowest at 6th degree polynomial with 0.51 as shown in Figure 2. Correspondingly for these 2 runs, the regressed PPG functions of were plotted against data in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

From the run with lowest CVSM score in

Figure 4, a long PPG count of 174 counts was observed, contributing to the poor fitting and low CVSM score. Physically, 174 counts of 50Hz sampling rate corresponds to a PPG count of 3.48 seconds which potentially originated from heart palpitations, sensor misdetection due to signal amplitude not reaching the 50% threshold or sensor noise as seen from scattered data points below 500 in

Figure 4. A continuous histogram of the highest CVSM per pre-journey set shows a central tendency towards 0.77 to 0.85 in Figure 5.

Figure 1: Discrete histogram showing the distribution of the degree of polynomial with highest CVSM per pre-journey set.

Figure 2: Scatter plot of CVSM of corresponding to degree of polynomial with highest CVSM per pre-journey set.

Figure 3: Regressed PPG function of pre-journey set of run 39, CVSM = 0.91, degree of polynomial = 8. Regressed function represented as red line, PPG data points represented as green crosses.

Figure 4: Regressed PPG function of pre-journey set of run 32, CVSM = 0.02, degree of polynomial = 6. Regressed PPG function represented as red line, PPG data points represented as green crosses.

Figure 5: Continuous histogram of highest CVSM per pre-journey set.

3.2. Convergence of PPG data in Journey Sets

For journey sets of each run, polynomial regression of PPG data converged at the 8th degree polynomial, shown in Figure. CVSM peaked at 9th degree polynomial with 0.98 and was lowest at 3rd degree polynomial with -0.17, shown in Figure. Corresponding these 2 runs, the regressed PPG functions were plotted against data in Figure 8 and

Figure 9. From the lowest CVSM in Figure 9, only a maximum of 16 intervals, approximately 0.32 seconds, was observed for 30 PPG counts within the journey set. However, with no resemblance to an PPG/ECG waveform, the poor fitting is likely due to hardware related factors since the same software algorithms were able to produce high CVSM and models resembling common PG/ECG waveform for the rest of the run. A continuous histogram of the highest CVSM per journey set shows tendency towards 0.91 to 0.94 in Figure.

Figure 6: Discrete histogram showing the distribution of the degree of polynomial with highest CVSM per journey set.

Figure 7: Scatter plot of CVSM of corresponding to degree of polynomial with highest CVSM per journey set.

Figure 8: Regressed PPG function of journey set of run 42, CVSM = 0.98 (highest), degree of polynomial = 9. Regressed PPG function represented as red line, PPG data points represented as green crosses.

Figure 9: Regressed PPG function of journey set of run 63, CVSM = -0.17 (lowest), degree of polynomial = 3. Regressed PPG function represented as red line, PPG data points represented as green crosses.

Figure 10: Continuous histogram of highest CVSM per journey set.

3.3. Reliability of Degree of Polynomial Matching

Reliability within this study was the rate of matching of the degree of polynomial between pre-journey and journey sets and calculated by dividing the number of matches by the total number of journey sets. The reliability of each run is shown in Figure 11 and ranges from 2% to 95%. The lowest reliability came from run 32, which is also the run with the lowest CVSM for its pre-journey set. The highest reliability came from run 16, pre-journey regressed function shown in Figure 12. While run 39, with highest CVSM pre-journey set, recorded a 0.79 reliability. Specific calculations for these 3 runs are tabulated in Table 2. The distribution of reliability tends towards the extremes between 0 to 1 as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 11: Reliability of degree of polynomial matching for each run.

Figure 12: Regressed PPG function of pre-journey set of run 16, CVSM = 0.65, degree of polynomial = 8. Regressed PPG function represented as red line, PPG data points represented as green crosses.

Table 2: Reliability calculations for runs 16, 32 and 39.

Run	Reference Set			Number of Journey Sets	Matches	Reliability
	Degree of Polynomial	CVSM	No. of Intervals of Longest PPG Count			
16	8	0.65	63	123	117	0.95
32	6	0.02	174	125	2	0.02
39	8	0.91	47	124	98	0.79

Figure 13: Continuous histogram of reliability scores.

With knowledge of the presence of long PPG counts lowering the model's goodness of fit from earlier pre-journey analysis, the distribution of reliability analyzed by plotting reliability against the maximum interval counts of the longest PPG within a pre-journey set, shown in Figure 14. The resulting reliability distribution can be clustered into (1) low reliability with 150 interval and above, (2) low reliability around 50 intervals and (3) high reliability around 50 intervals.

Figure 14: Scatter plot of reliability against number of intervals of longest PPG count in pre-journey set.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The convergence of PPG and reliability of degree of polynomial matching was studied for the autonomous hospital bed pushing framework. In terms of PPG convergence, it was observed that both pre-journey and journey sets converges to the same degree of polynomial which facilitates the establishment of a status quo in PPG vitals for the journey phase of the autonomous hospital bed operation. Even though the convergence was towards the 8th degree polynomial, it cannot be deemed as the only appropriate degree of polynomial to achieve. As seen from the CVSM distribution from journey sets in Figure 7, both 9th and 10th degree polynomials were able to achieve better CVSM scores than the 8th degree. In terms of reliability, a range of 2% to 95% was observed and influenced by long PPG counts potentially caused by heart palpitations or hardware related factors. Limitation of this work is the single subject population. Resulting from this work, the recommendations are (1) to improve PPG sensor towards hospital grade pulse oximetry devices to better isolate the cause of long PPG counts (2) increase population of study.

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